

Deliverable

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Project Acronym:		VRTogether		
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D5.8 - Documentation and technical fact sheets v2

Revision: 1.2

Authors: Susana Otero (i2CAT), Ana Revilla (Entropy), Iván Rodríguez(i2CAT)

Delivery date: M24

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Dissemination Level		
P	Public	x
C	Confidential, only for members of the consortium and the Commission Services	

Abstract: This deliverable is a compilation of all printed material produced so far, used for dissemination and communication purposes. In addition to the items compiled in D5.7, this deliverable includes new printed materials produced in the second year: 5 posters, 1 commercial fact sheet, 1 technical fact sheet. These materials were used in the different commercial and scientific events, such as ICT 2018, MMM 2019, ICT Open 2019, IEEE VR 2019, CERTH-ITI Open Day 2019, NEM 2019. ACM MMsvs 2019 and IBC 2019.

0.1	14/11/2018	Susana Otero	i2CAT	First release
1.1	17/09/2019	Iván Rodríguez	i2CAT	First draft of second iteration
1.2	27/09/2019	Pascal Perrot	Viaccess-Orca	Final review

Disclaimer

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Statement of originality:

This document contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document is a compilation of printed dissemination material (including technical information). In this second release, the materials provided in D5.7 are supplemented by updates to these documents (project image, commercial fact sheet), as well as newly created ones (5 posters and 2 technical fact sheets).

This wide range of printed communication materials have been produced to present the project and its outcomes. Contents have been specifically created to meet the needs of each channel/audience, always with a clear and appealing approach.

The materials have been used in the global events where the VRTogether project has been showcased, including ICT 2018, MMM 2019, ICT Open 2019, IEEE VR 2019, CERTH-ITI Open Day 2019, NEM 2019, ACM MMsys 2019 and IBC 2019.

Fact sheets were created with different approaches (technical, general info, commercial, etc.). In order to give detailed explanations of the developments achieved at various dissemination events. Initial versions were focused on general information about the project (i.e.: scope, objectives, and technologies to be developed) and technical insights of the pilots. Subsequent versions were later developed to present the achievements of the project and its current status.

Furthermore, a series of posters providing detailed information on specific topics was developed during this second year. An initial poster featuring a description of the first pilot, an overview of the configuration modes and a diagram showing the platform architecture was followed by a range of posters, each taking a different approach to the project, to support dissemination at public events.

The material is accessible and downloadable through the project website: <http://vrtogether.eu/project-outcomes/dissemination-materials/>

CONTRIBUTORS

First Name	Last Name	Company	e-Mail
Susana	Otero	I2CAT	susana.otero@i2cat.net
Iván	Rodríguez	i2CAT	ivan.rodriguez@i2cat.net
Pascal	Perrot	Viaccess-Orca	pascal.perrot@viaccess-orca.com

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1. INTRODUCTION

This document is a compilation of the printed dissemination materials (including technical information) produced within the VRTogether project from M14 to M24.

The document is mainly structured in two parts. A first part lists all the documents produced during the second year of project. The list provides also a brief description of the document. The second part of the document provides the documents.

2. PROJECT DOCUMENTATION

2.1. List of material

Name	Version	Description	Release date	Author
Logo	1.0	A logo that was initially used in internal documents and later would be improved.	2017 October 17	Entropy
Logo	2.0	Different formats of multi colored and dynamic logo	2017 November 12	Entropy
Project image	1.0	A stock image to have a recurrent resource to be used in the several dissemination materials that transmits the project concept.	2017 November 29	i2CAT
Project image	2.0	A stock image emphasizing the social side of the project.	2017 November 29	i2CAT
Poster	1.0	A poster that introduces the project and its objectives. This poster was used in order to present the project ImmersiaTV during the workshop "Collaboration Towards the Future of Media" (organised by the EU) in Brussels on October 10th, 2017. It shows the project objectives and milestones	2017 October 10	i2CAT
Poster	2.0	An A1 poster featuring a description of the first pilot, an overview of the configuration modes and a diagram showing the platform architecture. It has been displayed at VRTogether's lab nodes, as well as in events such as CERTH-ITI Open Day 2019 and NEM 2019.	2019 January 21	i2CAT
Poster Social VR	3.0	An A1 poster presenting a general overview of the project, focused on the pipelines, platform characteristics and products. It was displayed at VRTogether's booth at IBC 2019.	2019 July 19	i2CAT
Poster Products	3.0	An A1 poster detailing the actual exploitation opportunities, including 2 end-to-end products, 2 main components and 1 evaluation service. It was displayed at VRTogether's booth at IBC 2019.	2019 July 19	i2CAT
Poster Technological Innovations	3.0	An A1 poster detailing the platform architecture and the specific innovations in terms of technology	2019 July 19	i2CAT
Poster Pilots	3.0	An A1 poster detailing the roadmap and each of the pilots, as well as the evaluation methodology.	2019 July 19	i2CAT
Commercial Fact sheet	1.0	An item that introduces the project and has been frequently used in the more initial phase of period 1: IBC 2017, NEM Summit 2017, MMSYS2018 and TVX 2018	2017 November 29	i2CAT
Commercial	2.0	A flyer with a more commercial bias that can	2018	Entropy,

Fact sheet		be used in order to reach and engage the industrial stakeholders	September 13	i2CAT
Commercial Fact sheet	3.0	A slight update of v2.0. This accordion-fold brochure presents the project and its objectives, provides an updated overview of the pilots and lists VRTogether's potential products and main features. It was distributed at IBC 2019.	2019 September 6	Entropy, i2CAT
Technical fact sheet	1.0	Design of a general document that explains the main technical aspects of the first Pilot and the demo shown. It has been used during IBC2018.	2018 September 13	Entropy
Technical Fact sheet Web pipeline	2.0	An A4, double-sided fact sheet showing the key features of the end-to-end web-based framework. It was distributed at IBC 2019.	2019 July 24	i2CAT
Technical Fact sheet Volumetric video	2.0	An A4, double-sided fact sheet showing the key features of the volumetric video production system. It was distributed at IBC 2019.	2019 September 6	i2CAT
Roll up	1.0	A roll up designed to grasp visitors' attention during the IBC2018 and inviting them to test the demo. It contains a market-oriented claim, the members of the consortium and the EU flag.	2018 October 29	i2CAT

3. LOGO

3.1. v1.0

3.2. v2.0

4. PROJECT IMAGE

4.1. v1.0

4.2. v2.0

5. POSTER

5.1. v1.0

VR TOGETHER

In this project, our aim is to radically improve the experience by innovating in how media formats are used (i.e., how audio, video and graphics are captured, delivered and rendered at users' homes) demonstrating a significant improvement of **the feeling of being there together** and the **photorealistic quality of the content**.

OBJECTIVES

- A** Develop and integrate new media formats that deliver high quality photo-realistic content and create a strong feeling of co-presence in coherently integrated experiences.
- B** Adapt the existing production pipeline to capture and encode multiple media formats and integrate them with state-of-the-art post-production tools.
- C** Re-Design the distribution chain so such innovative content format can be orchestrated and delivered in a scalable manner.
- D** Develop appropriate Quality of Experience (QoE) metrics and evaluation methods to quantify the quality of these new social VR experiences.
- E** Maximize the impact of VR-Together can have on content creators, producers, distributors, tooling companies, service providers and the general audience.

MILESTONES

3 pilots addressing 3 different production format in a unified architecture.

- Intimate Concert**
Offline pilot to demonstrate that the innovative media format of VR-Together (orchestrating point clouds, 3DMesh based models and multiple video sources) can produce a more intimate and binding activity.
- Live news**
Live production of multi-source immersive content that takes the user to the location where news are occurring while sharing them with other people.
- Interactive Fiction**
Pilot to demonstrate how the VR-Together platform, in a custom-designed content production process, can allow for a novel form of content where users meet, and blend within the interactive immersive experience.

GRANT NUMBER 762111
DURATION 3 years (2017-2020)
BUDGET 3.9M€

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[@VRTogether_EU](#)

www.vrtogether.eu
sergi.fernandez@i2cat.net

This project has been funded by the European Commission as part of the H2020 program, under the grant agreement 762111

Project Coordinator & Technical Lead

VR Together's consortium has been strategically set up to consist of partners that cover all stages of the production chain in a well-balanced way. A combination of leading academic institutions **I2CAT, TNO, CWI, CERN, Artanim** together with industry actors **Future Lighthouse, Entropy, Motion Spell, Viaccess-Orca** spread over 5 European countries.

5.2. v2.0

VRTogether

AN END-TO-END SYSTEM FOR THE PRODUCTION AND DELIVERY OF PHOTOREALISTIC SOCIAL IMMERSIVE VIRTUAL REALITY EXPERIENCES

SOCIAL VR LIKE NEVER SEEN BEFORE

PILOT 1: POLICE INTERROGATION

Two users watch a police interrogation from the dark side of the room. After the interrogatory, the users can interact and discuss about the scene.

WEB BASED CONFIGURATION

A WebRTC powered full body reconstruction employing RGB + depth information.

TIME VARYING MESH CONFIGURATION

A 3D full body reconstruction employing meshes and using RabbitMQ for its transmission.

POINT CLOUD CONFIGURATION

A 3D full body reconstruction employing point clouds and working over DASH.

The diagram illustrates the end-to-end system architecture. It starts with two users (User 01 and User 02) who are captured. The **Capture** stage involves a 'Head Camera' and 'Body Camera' feeding into 'Stereocameras'. The **Encoding & Encapsulation** stage includes 'Encoder', 'Encapsulator', and 'Packager'. The **Delivery** stage uses 'RTSP' and 'Web Server'. The **Playback** stage involves 'Player', 'Stereocameras', 'User', and 'Control Panel'. The **Decimation** stage includes 'Projection Manager', 'Scene Manager', 'Scene Manager', 'Scene Manager', 'Scene Manager', 'Scene Manager', 'Scene Manager', and 'Scene Manager'. A 'Control' block is also shown at the bottom.

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This project has been funded by the European Commission under the Horizon 2020 programme, under the grant agreement 101019111.

5.3. v3.0

5.3.1. Social VR

AN END-TO-END SYSTEM FOR THE PRODUCTION AND DELIVERY OF

PHOTOREALISTIC SOCIAL IMMERSIVE VIRTUAL REALITY EXPERIENCES

SOCIAL VR LIKE NEVER SEEN BEFORE

VRTogether aims at enabling social Virtual Reality experiences that allow a natural interaction between **remote users immersed in a shared virtual environment** in an affordable way and with photo-realistic quality. It also explores the hybridization of content formats—2D, 3D, Point Clouds and Time Varying Meshes (TVM)—to achieve **the highest quality of experience possible** while keeping production costs under reasonable limits.

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VRTogether PIPELINES

WEB Home Based VR

 RGB-Depth

 3DoF+

 WebRTC

UNITY 3D Location Based VR

 TVM

 4DoF

 DASH

 Point Clouds

VRTogether PLATFORM CHARACTERISTICS

- Multimedia delivery chain
- Workflow development
- 3D rendering engines
- Encoding & encapsulation of content stream
- Live motion capture
- 3D characters reconstruction with TVMs or Point Clouds
- Data orchestration within the information flow

PRODUCTS

 Lightweight social VR service

 Volumetric data end to end transmission system

 4D Capture System

 Point Cloud MCU

 New protocol and metrics to evaluate social VR

5.3.2. Products

AN END-TO-END SYSTEM FOR THE PRODUCTION AND DELIVERY OF

PHOTOREALISTIC SOCIAL IMMERSIVE VIRTUAL REALITY EXPERIENCES

PRODUCTS

The VRTogether project is developing **2 end-to-end products** that offer a complete solution to experiment social Virtual Reality; **2 main components** that can be proposed as standalone components; and **1 evaluation service** for new protocols and metrics for social VR (sVR) evaluation.

Lightweight social VR service

E2E Solution
Real-time E2E communication system. Based on web technologies (HTML5, Javascript, WebRTC and WebGL APIs), combined with video coding and distribution standards like DASH, it provides an efficient VR based conferencing system.

Volumetric data end to end transmission system

Component
It allows any kind of volumetric data (Point Clouds or mesh) to be transmitted to a final system by including smart layers of filtering and compression.

4D Capture System

Component
It enables multi-RGBD, Point Cloud and TVM real time acquisition. The 4D Capture system will provide the opportunity to capture users even for XR applications since it will offer an automatic, smart HMD removal option.

Point Cloud – MCU

E2E Solution
A key and strategic part of a real time E2E communication system, which can be considered as holographic conferencing system.

New protocol and metrics to evaluate social VR

Service
A set of objective metrics that can monitor (and predict) QoE, in a software package; and a set of guidelines and protocol for others to follow, developed to meet the evaluation needs of a new medium such as social VR.

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5.3.3. Technological Innovations

AN END-TO-END SYSTEM FOR THE PRODUCTION AND DELIVERY OF

PHOTOREALISTIC SOCIAL IMMERSIVE VIRTUAL REALITY EXPERIENCES

TECHNOLOGICAL INNOVATIONS

VRTogether is innovating in terms of various user representation media in social-VR, enabling immersion and interaction between **multiple remote users** within VR environments.

Depth-sensors technology enable volumetric capturing thanks to RGB-D view acquisition. From a single RGB-D view processing to a rig of multiple RGB-D views, thanks to **mesh-based** and **point cloud-based** reconstruction algorithms, the production of low-latency volumetric video streams is now a true envision.

Aiming to provide technologies for highly responsive and realistic user interaction, VRTogether is innovating on **media encoding, transmission and rendering** in an efficient and orchestrated way.

To enhance immersion, VRTogether is researching on sophisticated **HMD removal** methods, targeting more natural interaction between VR users.

	LOCATION	PROCESS	DoF	STREAM
WEB	 Home Based VR	 RGB+Depth	 3DoF+	 WebRTC
UNITY 3D	 Location Based VR	 TVM Point Clouds	 6DoF	 DASH

- STREAMS (TVM, PC, 2D)
- LIVE STREAMS (2D BILLBOARD)
- STREAMS (ON DEMAND CONTENT)
- WEBSOCKETS (socket.io)
- - - - - COMMANDS

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5.3.4. Pilots

AN END-TO-END SYSTEM FOR THE PRODUCTION AND DELIVERY OF

PHOTOREALISTIC SOCIAL IMMERSIVE VIRTUAL REALITY EXPERIENCES

PILOTS

A coherent storyline across 3 pilots

1 Feeling of being there (presence) and of being there together (togetherness)

Two users watch a police interrogation of a murder suspect from the dark side of the room. During the experience, the users can interact and talk about the scene while seeing each other in a photo-realistic quality 3D representation.

2 COMING SOON

Live media and scalability

Four users are placed in a TV news studio where the presenter is giving an overview of the news of the day. When the murder is being reported, users are holo-ported to the crime scene where a journalist relates the details of the murder.

The final pilot will conclude the presented story, with users being able to interact with objects and characters in the scene, driving the scenario through their interactions.

3 Interaction and 6DoF

Users are able to interact remotely in a shared VR world

All their actions are delivered in real time

A 3D reconstruction of the users body is provided

You can see the other users interacting as themselves

EVALUATION METHODOLOGY

Objective Metrics

- Performance Metrics
- Users' behavior (gestures, head movements)

Subjective Metrics

- Questionnaires
- Semi-structured interviews

DEPLOYMENT

- Collaborative User Lab Inter-connected nodes in Greece, The Netherlands & Spain
- Scientific & Industrial events

VRTogether is assembling an end-to-end workflow for Social Virtual Reality content production. Development updates are presented through three pilots, three episodes of a **great story about a murder investigation**. The storyline exploits the uniqueness of the project, a team composed of technical and artistic experts, by creating a new experience that makes the most of the writing possibilities.

WATCH PILOT 1

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6. COMMERCIAL FACT SHEET

6.1. v1.0

In this project, our aim is to radically improve the experience by innovating in how media formats are used (i.e., how audio, video and graphics are captured, delivered and rendered at users' homes) demonstrating a significant improvement of the feeling of being there together and the photorealistic quality of the content.

VRTogether's consortium has been strategically set up to consist of partners that cover all stages of the production chain in a well-balanced way.

A combination of leading academic institutions (GCAT, TNO, CWI, GEMTH), Arnhem together with industry actors Future Lighthouse, Entropy, Motion Spell, Vaccara-Cica spread over 5 European countries.

MAIN OBJECTIVES

1. Develop and integrate user avatars to enable high quality photo-realistic content and create a strong feeling of presence in a shared virtual environment.
2. Adapt the existing production pipeline to capture and create multiple and distributed content for the production tools.
3. Design the distribution of content so that innovative content formats can be delivered to a wide range of devices.
4. Develop appropriate quality of experience (QoE) metrics and evaluation methods to quantify the quality of these new types of VR experiences.
5. Maximize the impact of VRTogether on the current and future content creators, publishers, leading companies, service providers and the general audience.

Deliverable Content
 Offer a platform to create and share high quality photo-realistic content and create a strong feeling of presence in a shared virtual environment.

Other aims
 Use the platform to create and share high quality photo-realistic content and create a strong feeling of presence in a shared virtual environment.

Interactive Content
 Offer a platform to create and share high quality photo-realistic content and create a strong feeling of presence in a shared virtual environment.

MILESTONES

6.2. v2.0

PILOTS

Three pilots, three different episodes of a great story about a murder investigation.

Pilot 1: Police interrogation

Two users watch a police interrogation from the dark side of the room. During the experience, the users can interact and talk about the scene while seeing each other in a photo-realistic quality 3D representation.

Pilot 2: Live scenario

Several users experience a live scenario: they are taken to a news broadcast set where, following the story, the background changes and they can view and examine the crime scene.

Pilot 3: Interactivity

Extending the experience of the other pilots, users interact with the virtual environment with cause-effect actions.

APPLICATIONS & USE CASES

Current Social Virtual Reality applications focus on abstract user representations, with simplified avatar representations.

VR-Together now offers the possibility of meeting friends, family and colleagues with a photo-realistic look-alike representation, which brings better support to a multitude of emerging applications, such as business meetings and educational experiences.

GOOD FOR

- Business meetings
- Family experiences
- Educational purposes
- Social networks
- Entertainment
- Games

MAIN FEATURES

The main characteristics of the VR-Together platform are:

- Multimedia delivery chain workflow development
- Live motion capture
- 3D rendering engines
- Encoding and encapsulation of content stream
- 3D characters reconstruction with Time Varying Meshes or Point Clouds
- Data orchestration within the information flow

EXPECTED IMPACT

To set a new standard in social VR using off-the-shelf products

OBJECTIVES

1. Develop and integrate new media formats that deliver high quality photo-realistic content and create a strong feeling of co-presence in coherently integrated experience.
2. Adapt the existing production pipeline to capture and encode multiple media formats and integrate them with state-of-the-art post-production tools.
3. Re-Design the distribution chain so such innovative content format can be orchestrated and delivered in a scalable manner.
4. Develop appropriate Quality of Experience (QoE) metrics and evaluation methods to quantify the quality of these new social VR experiences.
5. Maximize the impact of VR-Together can have on content creators, producers, distributors, tooling companies, service providers and the general audience.

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PARTNERS

This project has been funded by the European Commission as part of the H2020 program, under the grant agreement 762111

PHOTO-REALISTIC IMMERSIVE CONTENT

VR-Together project aims to offer ground-breaking social Virtual Reality (VR) experiences between users located in remote domestic scenarios, based on photo-realistic immersive content, in a cost-effective manner.

VR-Together's consortium has been strategically set up to consist of partners that cover all stages of the production chain in a well-balanced way.

A combination of leading research institutions i2CAT, TNO, CWI, CERTH, Artanim together with industry actors Entropy, Motion Spell, Viaccess-Orca spread over 4 European countries.

6.3. v3.0

OBJECTIVES

1. **Develop and integrate new media formats** that deliver high quality photo-realistic content and create a strong feeling of co-presence in coherently integrated experience.
2. **Adapt the existing production pipeline** to capture and encode multiple media formats and integrate them with state-of-the-art post-production tools.
3. **Re-design the distribution chain** so such innovative content format can be orchestrated and delivered in a scalable manner.
4. **Develop appropriate Quality of Experience (QoE) metrics and evaluation methods** to quantify the quality of these new social VR experiences.
5. **Maximize the impact that VRTogether can have** on content creators, producers, distributors, tooling companies, service providers and the general audience.

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PARTNERS

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AN END-TO-END SYSTEM FOR THE PRODUCTION AND DELIVERY OF
PHOTOREALISTIC SOCIAL IMMERSIVE VIRTUAL REALITY EXPERIENCES

SOCIAL VR LIKE NEVER SEEN BEFORE

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PILOTS

Development updates are presented through three pilots, three episodes of a great story about a murder investigation.

Pilot 1: Feeling of being there (presence) and of being there together (togetherness)

Two users watch a police interrogation of a murder suspect from the dark side of the room. During the experience, the users can interact and talk about the scene while seeing each other in a photo-realistic quality 3D representation.

Users are able to interact remotely in a shared VR world

All their actions are delivered in real time

A 3D reconstruction of the users body is provided

You can see the other users interacting as themselves!

Pilot 2: Live media and scalability

Four users are placed in a TV news studio where the presenter is giving an overview of the news of the day. When the murder is being reported, users are holo-ported to the crime scene where a journalist relates the details of the murder.

Pilot 3: Interaction and 6DoF

The final pilot will conclude the presented story, with users being able to interact with objects and characters in the scene, driving the scenario through their interactions.

APPLICATIONS & USE CASES

Current Social Virtual Reality applications focus on abstract user representations, with simplified avatar representations.

VRTogether now offers the possibility of meeting friends, family and colleagues with a photo-realistic look-alike representation, which brings better support to a multitude of emerging applications, such as business meetings and educational experiences.

PRODUCTS

MAIN FEATURES

- Multimedia delivery chain
- 3D rendering engines
- Workflow development
- Live motion capture
- Encoding & encapsulation of content stream
- 3D characters reconstruction with TVMs or Point Clouds
- Data orchestration within the information flow

EXPECTED IMPACT

To set a new standard in social VR using off-the-shelf products

7. TECHNICAL FACT SHEET

7.1. v1.0

WEB BASED CONFIGURATION

Capture and delivery

This is a basic web-based configuration employed in VR-Together. For the capturing process, the Kinect V2 or the RealSense D415 camera is used. For the streaming process, the WebRTC framework is used.

The foreground/background segmentation is based on the depth image. A reference image (RGB + depth) is captured before a user is present in the scene. Next, each frame of the captured video is processed. The depth image of each frame is compared to the reference frame to determine the foreground, i.e. the image of the user. This depth map is cleaned up, and applied to the RGB image to retrieve the user's RGB foreground image. The sequence of images, retrieved in this way, is offered as a virtual webcam to the WebRTC framework.

The delivery is currently based on the SimpleWebRTC framework. The Media Capture API is used to retrieve both the virtual webcam and the HMD's microphone. Sessions are set up between the various users under supervision of the Orchestration component. The media is exchanged in a peer-to-peer fashion between the clients involved in the session.

Additional developments in this configuration involve:

- Applying the captured RGB-D into a Point Cloud that is overlaid on the captured users position, to show a self view;
- Streaming the captured depth images to other clients to allow a 3D image reconstruction at the receiving side;

Play-out

For rendering, the A-Frame framework is used, which is based on WebGL. In this framework, various objects can be combined into a single VR experience. In the basic scenario, a 360 degree photo is used as a virtual environment. In this environment, 2D planes are placed at the other users' positions, and their video (containing only their foreground) is displayed on these 2D planes. The accompanying audio, which is synchronized with the video by using the WebRTC framework, is also placed at the users' positions.

Object-based audio is supported through the integration of the Google Resonance framework. For display of 3D objects, i.e. self-representation of a user or representation of other users, custom shaders that support the employed RGB + depth format for display in a 3D fashion have been developed while the 3D room model object is supported by A-Frame by default.

This project has been funded by the European Commission as part of the Horizon program under the grant agreement 101017111.

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PLATFORM ARCHITECTURE

COMPONENTS DESCRIPTION

The software architecture of the end-to-end VR-Together (i.e. from capture to consumption chain) is comprised of 5 main components. These components serve as a basis of the integrated platform structure, and each one of them is a conceptual entity related to a general task within the end-to-end communication system.

The Capturing component captures / produces the visual and audio data, performs content reconstruction tasks and synchronizes the captures audio and video signals.

The Encoding & Encapsulation component encodes, encapsulates and packages the audio and video signals received from the previous component into one single stream.

The Delivery component makes this content available for consumption on the network.

The Orchestration component provides end-users with the information necessary to initiate a communication session over the VR-Together platform.

The Play-out component is responsible for rendering and presentation of the immersive contents. It includes the controls for the shared virtual scenarios and end-users' representation. It includes modules for unpackaging, denoising and decoding and synchronizing the audio-visual content.

TIME VARYING MESH CONFIGURATION

Capture and delivery

A full-body 3D user representation is reconstructed (real-time) in a 3D mesh form, i.e. a set of connected vertices and polygons applying UV texturing. The capturing of color and depth information is realized by multiple calibrated RGB-D cameras including the processing of spatial mapping and alignment of the captured 2.5D data into 3D, resulting in a watertight 3D TVM which is reconstructed in real-time. TVMs contain multiple RGB textures, one per RGB-D device, as well as the 3D geometrical information of the mesh, i.e. the vertices, polygons and the corresponding normal vectors.

Due to the data intensive nature of TVMs, compression for fast and efficient transmission via web-based scenarios is necessary. TVMs are compressed both on the level of textures as well as in that of the 3D mesh. 3D data is compressed employing state-of-the-art methods (e.g. Draco, Corto) while for the textures the TurboJPEG library is used. Subsequently, the compressed data are serialized (packaged) and distributed by a RabbitMQ server, allowing for the VR-Together player to connect and retrieve the transferred information in real-time.

Play-out

Following the information retrieval at the player's side, the packaged TVMs are deserialized and decoded prior to the final step, namely the TVM rendering. To this end, the transferred RGB textures are blended to colorize the 3D mesh within a unity 3D scene. In particular, the textures are weighted based on the confidence given by the angle difference between the normal of the corresponding polygons and the camera view axis, thus, higher angles correspond to lower confidence.

The audio is mixed locally to reflect the position of every audio object, and is affected by the position and rotation of each user and element in the virtual environment.

Such a practice provides a photo-realistic 3D environment where 3D assets, stereoscopic billboards and 3D user representations are seamlessly presented in a synchronized manner.

Each user starts a session where he or she can socially interact with the other person, being each one of them able to experience a different part of the story via their Head Mounted Displays (HMDs).

<https://github.com/jogajalaco>
<https://github.com/leon-sil-wahlstrom>
<https://github.com/jogajalaco>

POINT CLOUD CONFIGURATION

Capture and delivery

A volumetric representation of the user is captured in real-time as a Point Cloud, i.e. a set of independent points in space, each associated to its spatial coordinates and an RGB triplet indicating the color of the point. The capture is performed by a signal acquisition module, developed by CWI, that merges the data captured by multiple texture + depth Intel RealSense sensors, positioned around the user. The capture module outputs a raw Point Cloud frame and the corresponding capture timestamp at a variable frame rate.

The raw Point Cloud would require extremely high bandwidth to be transmitted over bandwidth-limited networks. Therefore, in order to enable delivery of the Point Cloud signal, each Point Cloud frame is delivered as input to a lossy encoder, developed by CWI, which reduces the bitrate needed to represent the volumetric signal, by removing visual redundancy. The output of the encoding module is an encoded Point Cloud frame. The capture timestamp is also included in the encoded stream to enable their synchronized presentation.

Finally, each encoded Point Cloud frame is packed into a DASH segment (i.e., m4s file), by an application based on the Signals framework, developed by Motion Spell. The m4s files corresponding to temporally consecutive Point Cloud frames are stored on a DASH server, ready to be delivered via HTTP.

Play-out

The incoming packaged Point Cloud frames are handled at the receiver side by using GStreamer framework. An HTTP connection is established to first obtain the MPD and then request the DASH segments composing the stream. From the DASH segments, the Point Cloud structure is extracted and sent to the Point Cloud decoder. The inserted timestamps at the capture side are extracted and used by a developed synchronization module to allow the presentation of all incoming data in a synchronized manner.

A native Point Cloud renderer module was developed to enable user representation in that format. It is based on the wrapper for Unity of Intel RealSense SDK 2.0, which transforms the raw data from the RGB Camera and the Depth Sensor into a Unity 3D mesh.

<https://github.com/jogajalaco>
<https://github.com/leon-sil-wahlstrom>
<https://github.com/leon-sil-wahlstrom>

7.2. v2.0

7.2.1. Web pipeline

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 761974.

END-TO-END WEB-BASED FRAMEWORK TO BUILD AND CONSUME SHARED AND SOCIAL VR EXPERIENCES

FEATURES

Simplified Technology Pipeline

- Use of Web-based components:
 - » WebRTC for communication.
 - » WebVR, WebGL for rendering.
 - » React, Node.js and A-Frame for UI frontend.
- Using common off-the-shelf and consumer grade equipment for capture and display.

Fully orchestrated

- Session management, with per session setup options.
- Multi-person capture and rendering management.
- Synchronisation of live and virtual content.

REAL-TIME LIVE CAPTURE

- Live 3D capture of users using RGB-D cameras (e.g. Kinect or Realsense).
- Provide self-view and HMD removal for local user.

PEER-TO-PEER OR BRIDGED COMMUNICATION

- Communication service through WebRTC.
- Peer-to-peer or if needed for scalability through a VR bridge, combining all individual participant's streams in one large stream.

EASY INTEGRATION OF VIRTUAL ENVIRONMENT

- Support for photo-realistic 360 video and virtual 3D environments.
- Multiple concurrent sources possible, eg. live streaming video in a virtual environment.

SIMPLIFIED TECHNOLOGY PIPELINE

WEB ARCHITECTURE OVERVIEW

VRTogether

AN END-TO-END SYSTEM FOR THE PRODUCTION AND DELIVERY OF PHOTOREALISTIC SOCIAL IMMERSIVE VIRTUAL REALITY EXPERIENCES

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www.vrtogether.eu

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7.2.2. Volumetric video

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 761974.

END-TO-END VOLUMETRIC VIDEO PRODUCTION SYSTEM FOR IMMERSIVE VR EXPERIENCES

TECHNOLOGY FEATURES

Portable

- Flexible and light-weight sensor calibration.

Low-cost

- Low-specification hardware resources for multi-RGBD data acquisition.
- Off-the-shelf RGBD sensors (i.e. Intel RealSense D400 series, Azure Kinect DK).

Scalable

- Support of variant number of sensors to alter the associated equipment cost and complexity, depending on the level of geometry detail and visual quality.

VOLUMETRIC VIDEO PRODUCTION

- Real-time (online) volumetric media streaming.
- Support of live self-view representation to boost immersion.
- Content creation through volumetric media recording and post-processing.

REAL-TIME VOLUMETRIC VIDEO COMPRESSION

- State-of-the-art geometry libraries integration.
- Multi-view texture compression.

EASY INTEGRATION OF VIRTUAL ENVIRONMENT

- Game engine plug & play compatibility (e.g. Unity3D, Unreal Engine 4).
- Support of photo-realistic 360° and 3D environments.
- 6 Degrees of Freedom for the user.

SIMPLIFIED TECHNOLOGY PIPELINE

NATIVE ARCHITECTURE OVERVIEW

VRTogether

AN END-TO-END SYSTEM FOR THE PRODUCTION AND DELIVERY OF PHOTOREALISTIC SOCIAL IMMERSIVE VIRTUAL REALITY EXPERIENCES

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8. ROLL-UP

8.1. v1.0

The poster features a woman wearing a VR headset, smiling, against a warm orange and pink background. The text is centered and reads: 'VRTogether PHOTO-REALISTIC IMMERSIVE CONTENT SOCIAL VR DEMO Available to try now!'. At the bottom, there is a row of logos for various partners and funders.

VRTogether
PHOTO-REALISTIC IMMERSIVE CONTENT
SOCIAL VR DEMO
Available to try now!

i2cat **CERTH** **CWI** **TNO** **innovation for life** **European Commission**
ENTROPY **viaccess-orca** **MOTION SPELL** **ertanim**
This project has been funded by the European Commission as part of the H2020 program, under the grant agreement 762111